

STRUCTURAL MODELS OF ANATOMICAL TERMS OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE

Shodmonov Diyorbek Obid ugli

2nd year student Faculty of Medicine-1 of Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract. The article is devoted to a systematic consideration of units of Latin anatomical terminology. The purpose of the work is to identify all structural models of Latin terms functioning in modern medical science and their typological representation. Scientific novelty is due to the systematic approach to the description of anatomical terms of the Latin language, as well as the fact that for the first time the structural typology of Latin anatomical terminological units and their quantitative relationship are established.

Key words: and phrases: Latin language; anatomical terminology; multicomponent terms; single-component terms.

Due to well-known historical events, the Latin language has become the basis for the formation of terminology systems in various fields of science and technology for many European languages. In the development of medical terminology, the role of the Latin language can hardly be overestimated, since to this day it is used as a universal system that promotes mutual understanding among physicians around the world thanks to the established unified terminological base, which, despite the fact of the “death” of the Latin language as a language of communication, nevertheless continues function within the framework of rapidly developing medical science.

In this sense, consideration of the system of anatomical terms of the Latin language, its resources, lexical means, as well as the actual inventory of different structural models of terms seems relevant both for linguists in general, which does not pay much attention to the Latin language, and for terminology in particular. Achieving the goal involves solving the following tasks: – selection of an inventory of terminological units of anatomical terminology of the Latin language; – classification of terms according to structural models; – establishment of typological models of terms within multicomponent models; – identification of the predominant part-verbal structures of anatomical terms in the Latin language.

The object of the study was the terminological units of Latin anatomical terminology. The subject of the study was the structural features of anatomical terms, on the basis of which a typology of structural models of anatomical terms in the Latin

language was compiled. The practical significance of the work lies in the fact that its results can be used in teaching courses on terminology, as well as the Latin language in medical universities. The main body of the study consisted of 7759 differently structured terminological units of Latin anatomical terminology. In the course of the work, such research methods were used as the descriptive method in the totality of its methods of analysis, synthesis in the process of selection and classification of factual material, the method of structural analysis and elements of the quantitative method in identifying and calculating the representation of various structural models in the system of anatomical terminology of the Latin language.

The theoretical basis of the study was the provisions of a number of works in such areas as terminology, structural and semantic features of terms, properties of terms and their differences from commonly used vocabulary, etc. The concept of "term" itself was the subject of discussion in various sciences: linguistics, philosophy, onomasiology, logic. At the same time, until now there is no consensus on the essence of this concept, and the number of definitions of the term reached even in the last century.

However, the common thing that can be identified in different definitions of the term is that the term is an element of a terminology system or a word/phrase denoting the concept of a special branch of knowledge. The status of terms-word combinations also cannot be called definite in modern linguistics, since depending on the number of components, terms-word combinations are called two- and multi-component. At the same time, the main discussion revolves around two-component terms, which some linguists classify as multi-component, while others consider them as a separate group. The latter define a multicomponent term (MCT) as a stable terminological combination with more than two significant components.

In the framework of this work, a term is understood as a word or phrase that has all the properties of a term, such as stability, unity of meaning, unambiguity, and denotes the concept of a certain professional field. At the same time, the object of our research becomes the entire system of terminological units of anatomical terminology of the Latin language, within which one-, two-, three-, etc. are distinguished. -component terms.

The difference between single-component and multi-component terms lies in the number of term elements. One-component terms consist of one term element, two-component terms include two significant lexemes, while the structure of

multicomponent terms consists of three or more components, expressed by significant parts of speech.

As part of the study of structural models of Latin anatomical terminology, 7759 terms of different structures were analyzed. Quantitative data and percentage of the total number of anatomical terms in the Latin language of terms one-, two-, three, etc.

The noun is the most common component in the anatomical Latin term; its share among other parts of speech was 53.4%, which is due to the tendency of the anatomical terminology terminology system to nominalize. The component expressed by an adjective was 45.6% in our study. The components expressed by the participle and numeral are few in number. They are 0.8% and 0.2% respectively. A possible continuation of the study seems to be the study of ways to translate Latin anatomical terms into Russian and English.

Literature:

1. Karimovna, Y. S., & Farxodovna, R. K. VISION. THE MAIN VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN ADOLESCENTS. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych.*, 45.
2. Ученых, Е. С. 12 (69), 2019 LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS Nuritdinova Zulkhumor Shamsievna Head of Chair in Samarkand State Medical Institute. *Yorova Sayora Karimovna English teacher of Samarkand State Medical Institute*, 9, 26.
3. Karimovna, Y. S., Erkinovna, T. N., & Agwan, A. (2023). MODERN EDUCATION AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT NURTURING GLOBAL CITIZENS IN THE 21ST CENTURY. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(11), 292-294.
4. Saydullaevna, N. N., & Karimovna, Y. S. COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING”, “ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. In *Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции* (p. 135).
5. Saydullaevna, N. N., & Karimovna, Y. S. COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING”, “ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. In *Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции* (p. 135).

6. Karimovna, Y. S. (2020). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF A SPECIALIST. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(4)*.
7. Karimovna, Y. S., & Sachdeva, L. (2023). DIFFERENT APPROACHES AND ISSUES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI, 3(5), 226-229*.
8. Karimovna, Y. S., & Farxodovna, R. K. THE EFFECT OF SLEEP ON STUDENT PERFORMANCE. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych., 26*.
9. Shamsievna, N. Z., & Karimovna, Y. S. LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS. *ЕВРАЗИЙСКИЙ СОЮЗ УЧЕНЫХ (ЕСУ), 32*.
10. Karimovna, Y. S., Kenjabaevna, A. P., Bakhodirovna, E. M., & Mallaevna, N. S. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES. DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE, *2 (2), 10–13*.
11. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 5341-5352*.
12. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 337-339*.
13. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences, 1(3), 192-196*.
14. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 1(1), 199-201*.
15. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald, 8, 221-224*.

16. Шарипов, Б. С. (2022). TIL BIRLIKLARINING NUTQDA FAOLLASHUVI HAQIDA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(1).
17. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.
18. Makhmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR.
19. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.
20. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.
21. Makhmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.
22. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Modern Methods of Teaching Latin and Medical Terminology in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 190-192.
23. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimoviche, S. B., & Arzimurodoviche, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.
24. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
25. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.

26. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.
27. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).
28. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
29. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.
30. Isroilova, M., & Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME OBSERVATIONS ON LATIN PRONUNCIATION AND SPELLING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(7), 127-129.
31. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
32. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). TRANSLATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND BASIC MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY CLASSES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 100-103.
33. Махмудов, З. М., & Шарипов, Б. С. Талабаларнинг фанни яхши ўрганишлари учун психо–эмоционал таъсир этишда халқ мақол ва маталларидан тўғри фойдаланиш (лотин тили ва тиббий терминология фани мисолида). *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 112.
34. Bektoshevna, E. D., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). LATIN AND GREC TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF STUDY OF OPERATIVE SURGERY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(6), 66-72.
35. Sharipov Bobur Salimovich. (2023). ESSENTIAL COMMENTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO THE ORIGIN OF CLINICAL TERMS AND

FEATURES OF CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(6), 144–148. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/296>

36. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). SOME THOUGHTS ON THE IMPORTANCE AND HISTORY OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN WORLD LANGUAGES. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 49-53.

37. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).

38. Yorova, S. K., & Khakberdiyeva, V. J. K. (2021). DOCTOR AND PATIENT. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 1478-1480.

39. Yorova, S. (2023). TO STUDY MEDICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND GREEK LANGUAGES. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 166-170.

40. Aitmuratova, P., Yorova, S., & Esanova, M. (2023). THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR LIFE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 161-164.

41. Yorova, S., Aytmuratova, P., Esanova, M., & Normurodova, S. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MEDICAL FIELD OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(2), 10-13.

42. Yorova, S. K., & Iqbal, I. (2023). HISTORY OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(9), 158-164.

43. Normurodova, S. M., & Yorova, S. K. (2023). Nemis tili frazeologik birikmalari va tilning lug'at boyligi. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 1672-1675.

44. Yorova, S. K. (2017). The concept “health” in the English lingual culture. In *Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives* (pp. 58-60).

45. Askarovich, B. S., Karimovna, Y. S., Sobirovich, X. Y., & Bakhodirovna, E. M. (2022). TEACHING MATH IN ENGLISH TO UNIVERSITIES AND

INSTITUTIONS'STUDENTS FOR TAKING GMAT CERTIFICATE. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 1600-1604.

46. Yorova, S., & Nasirkhan, A. (2023). MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF TRAUMATOLOGICAL, ORTHOPEDICS AND NEUROSURGICAL DISEASES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(11), 149-152.

47. Karimovna, Y. S., & Holalkere, V. S. (2023). DEMYSTIFYING PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY: UNDERSTANDING MEDICINAL FORMS AND FREQUENTLY USED SEGMENTS. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(4), 10-13.

48. Yorova, S. A. Y. O. R. A., & Nasimova, S. O. H. I. B. A. (2019). The ways of teaching languages at medical institutions.